

Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Pain Disorders in Mothers with Disabled Children in Iran

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Abstract:

Purpose:-The aim of this study was to investigate the prevalence of musculoskeletal- related pain in mothers carrying and lifting their disabled children for at least one year. **[Method]** Prevalence of musculoskeletal related pain was evaluated in different sites such as neck and shoulder, elbow, wrist, back and legs in seventy of mothers with disabled children (mean age of 30.2 ± 5.3 years old). The prevalence of depression was also investigated using a questionnaire. **[Results]** Prevalence of musculoskeletal related pain was more than expected in these mothers. Among pain in different sites, back pain was the most prevalent (84.1%). The prevalence of depression was also high (76.8%). **[Conclusion]** Musculoskeletal-related pains are more prevalent than expected in care givers especially mothers lifting and carrying their disabled children during non-ambulatory phase. Professionals involved in the care of children should also help parents to cope with the burden of caregiving as musculoskeletal-related pains and depression.

Key words: Care givers, musculoskeletal- related pain, depression, disability, children.

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